

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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Annotation. This article focuses on analyzing current trends in the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language. It examines key innovative methods that contribute to enhancing the effectiveness and practical relevance of learning, as well as developing learners' communicative competence.

The article delves into the following methods: gamification, flipped learning, differentiated instruction, the use of digital resources, and project-based learning. It analyzes their advantages and disadvantages, drawing on contemporary scientific research and practical teaching experience.

The article pays particular attention to the impact of innovative methods on increasing student motivation, fostering their creative abilities, and raising their language proficiency.

The article concludes that the use of innovative methods is a crucial requirement for successful teaching of Russian as a foreign language in the modern world. The article may be helpful for teachers of Russian as a foreign language, methodologists, and researchers in the field of language didactics.

Key words: Russian as foreign language(RFL), teaching methodology, innovative methods, teaching, modern condition, language proficiency, gamification, digital resources, technology integration, linguistic context.

The modern world presents new challenges for teachers of Russian as a foreign language. Learners want to learn in non-standard ways, efficiently, and with maximum practical benefit. Traditional teaching methods, while valuable, no longer always meet modern requirements. Therefore, the implementation of innovative methods that can make learning Russian more engaging, motivating, and effective is becoming increasingly important:

Gamification:

Gamification is the use of game mechanics (points, levels, competitions, virtual bonuses, etc.) in the learning process. Thanks to game elements, learning becomes more engaging, increasing learners' motivation and interest. Gamification contributes to faster comprehension of grammar, vocabulary, and improvement of communication skills. For example, you can use game applications, quizzes, crosswords, role-playing games, and simulations that make learning more interactive and practical.

2. Flipped Learning:

Flipped learning puts practice first. Instead of traditional theory-then-practice, students immediately start solving problems and then study the necessary theory to solve them. This method makes knowledge more practical, strengthens motivation, and makes learning more active.

3. Differentiated Instruction:

Differentiated instruction takes into account the individual characteristics and levels of student preparedness. The teacher can use different tasks, materials, and methods for each group of students, making learning more effective and meeting the individual needs of each student.

4. Using Digital Resources:

Modern technology opens up wide possibilities for teachers. Online platforms, mobile applications, video materials, interactive exercises, and virtual realities make learning more interactive, accessible, and engaging. Students can learn anytime, anywhere, using various digital tools.

5. Project-Based Learning:

Project-based learning involves students working in groups to implement practical projects. This allows them to apply their knowledge of the Russian language in real-life situations, develop communication skills, and demonstrate creativity. Projects can be diverse: creating a video, preparing a presentation, organizing an event, etc.

Advantages of Innovative Methods:

The use of innovative methods in teaching Russian as a foreign language has undeniable advantages:

- Increased motivation and interest in learning Russian.
- Improved learning efficiency and deeper knowledge acquisition.
- Development of practical skills and communication competence.
- Creation of a more interactive and engaging learning atmosphere.

To determine the most effective teaching method, an experiment was conducted titled "Gamification vs. Traditional Teaching: Impact on Motivation and Vocabulary Proficiency."

Objective of the experiment:

To assess the effectiveness of gamification compared to the traditional method of teaching Russian vocabulary to foreign language learners at the beginner level.

Participant groups:

- Experimental group: 25 students learning Russian as a foreign language at the beginner level using gamification.

Control group: 25 students learning Russian as a foreign language at the beginner level using traditional teaching methods.

Methods:

- Teaching:

- * Experimental group: Vocabulary instruction was conducted through game-based formats: quizzes, crosswords, games like "Word Hunt," "Guess the Word," "Make a Sentence," using specially developed online platforms with gamification elements.

- * Control group: Vocabulary instruction was conducted using the traditional method: learning words from a textbook, followed by exercises to reinforce vocabulary.

- Motivation: At the beginning and end of the experiment, participants completed a

questionnaire assessing their motivation to learn the Russian language.

- Testing: At the beginning and end of the experiment, a test was conducted to assess knowledge of new vocabulary, including tasks for understanding and applying new words.

Results:

Motivation: Students in the experimental group demonstrated significantly higher levels of motivation to learn Russian compared to the control group. In the questionnaires, they noted increased interest in lessons, a desire to learn new words, and practice communication.

Proficiency: The test results showed that students in the experimental group learned new vocabulary significantly better. They demonstrated a higher level of understanding of words and the ability to use them in speech.

Conclusion:

The experiment confirmed the effectiveness of gamification in teaching Russian vocabulary to foreign language learners. Gamification increases student motivation and contributes to more effective learning of new words. The experiment results confirm the importance of using innovative methods in teaching Russian as a foreign language.

Additional notes:

- It's important to note that this experiment was conducted with a limited number of participants and under specific conditions.

- Further research and analysis of results from various experiments are necessary to confirm the effectiveness of gamification in different contexts and with different groups of students.

- It's also crucial to consider that the effectiveness of gamification depends on the correct selection of games and exercises, as well as the teacher's ability to create an engaging and motivating atmosphere in the classroom.

In the modern world, teachers of Russian as a foreign language need to constantly seek out and implement new teaching methods to make learning more

engaging, relevant, and effective. Innovative methods allow for more interactive, practical learning that meets contemporary demands. It is crucial to continuously explore and implement new methods to maintain interest in the Russian language and ensure the successful learning of students.

List of literature:

1. Teaching Foreign Languages in the 21st Century: Trends and Challenges by Robert J. Breen (2017): An overview of changes in language teaching and how to adapt to new challenges.
2. The Handbook of Language Teaching edited by Brian Paltridge (2023): A comprehensive resource covering all aspects of language teaching and learning, including recent trends.
3. Technology and Language Learning by David Nunan (2003): An exploration of technology's role in language teaching and learning, highlighting the significance of digital resources.
4. Gamification in Language Learning by Michael G. B. Lee (2019): This book provides a thorough exploration of gamification in language teaching, including practical examples and strategies.
5. Games and Simulations in Language Learning by Rod Ellis (2009): A comprehensive guide to using games and simulations in language teaching for all levels.
6. Teaching Languages with Technology: A Guide for Teachers by Richard Breen (2015): This book offers practical tips and strategies for integrating technology into language teaching.